

HPC: GPU BACKEND OF ROOT

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

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This project aims to increase the performance of RooFit, a statistical modelling library of ROOT, by implementing more mathematical functions for the GPU backend. ROOT is a C++ software library used for data analysis in high-energy physics, particularly used by LHC experiments. Given the growing intricacy of LHC analyses and the expanding sizes of the datasets, recent RooFit developments focused on speeding up process execution with GPUs which can achieve up to 50x of speedup compared to a classical CPU with one core.

Some of the mathematical operations supported by RooFit that were implemented for the CPU had no support for the GPU. One of the main goals of this project was to tackle the computation of numeric integrals and its implementation for the GPU, which is actually what is limiting the performance for the most costly realistic use cases.

ABSTRACT

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In this project report, I present an innovative exploration conducted as part of my role as a CERN Openlab Summer Student 2023 within the ROOT team at CERN. This endeavour revolves around the implementation and optimization of the Kahan Summation algorithm on NVIDIA GPU architecture, aiming to enhance the accuracy of numerical computations involving floating-point arithmetic meanwhile decreasing the time execution needed to compute these calculations avoiding extra memory transfers between CPU and GPU. As well as adding more types of PDF (Probability Density Functions) to the GPU backend of RooFit and an introduction to the computation of numerical integrals in the GPU.

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1 Introduction

To understand the problems faced in this project, the main goal behind each of the solutions faced is reducing time execution by implementing or adapting mathematical functions to the GPU backend of RooFit.

2 Implementation of unsupported PDFs for the GPU

One of RooFit's features is to select likelihood evaluation mode, where the same C++ code is compiled for both CPU and GPU. Depending on the parameter passed to the `fitTo()` function [1] the execution will run in one or the other. More information about this toolkit is in [4] and [1].

```
power.fitTo(*data, PrintLevel(-1));
exppoly.fitTo(*data, PrintLevel(-1), BatchMode("cuda"));
```

Listing 1: Example of the call to the function with for CPU and GPU backend respectively.

The code snippet [2] is compiled in both the form of a standard C++ function and a CUDA kernel, contingent upon specific preprocessor definitions. With the utilization of "rooglobal", the "BatchesHandle" class functions as a reference to either host or device memory, and the "BEGIN" and "STEP" macros establish either event iteration (in the CPU scenario) or standard grid strides (when employed within a CUDA kernel). An example of this feature is the evaluation of a generalized power function [2]: $\sum_{i=0}^n a_i * x^{b_i}$.

```
__rooglobal__ void computePower(BatchesHandle batches)
{
    const int nCoef = batches.extraArg(0);
    Batch x = batches[0];

    for (size_t i = BEGIN; i < batches.getNEvents(); i += STEP) {
        batches._output[i] = 0.0;
        for (int k = 0; k < nCoef; ++k) {
            batches._output[i] += batches[2 * k + 1][i]
                * std::pow(x[i], batches[2 * k + 2][i]);
        }
    }
}
```

Listing 2: C++ function that computes the Power PDF which is compiled for both the GPU and the CPU backends.

3 Kahan-Summation algorithm for Nvidia GPU

The algorithm for the Kahan-Summation (the importance of which will be explained in section 3.3) was already implemented in the CPU but there was no implementation for the GPU. The array had to be transferred from the GPU VRAM (GPU's RAM) to CPU RAM to compute the Kahan-Summation and then copy it back to the GPU to continue the computation. Hence,

it was spending time on memory transfers, memory bandwidth and energy consumption. Since the data were already in the GPU VRAM, it would be far more efficient and faster to be able to compute the Kahan-Summation directly in the GPU.

3.1 Negative Log Likelihood (NLL)

The Negative Log-Likelihood (NLL) is frequently used in statistical modelling and machine learning. The NLL is used as a loss function to estimate the parameters of a model that best describes the observed data.

The main idea that we will consider of the NLL function is that, for large data sets, many additions (or subtractions) are going to be done. The precision of the add instruction with floating point variables is limited when dealing with decimal numbers. More details about this are in the following sections.

The formula for the NLL with which we are going to be working with is the NLL for unbinned fits:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n -\log(P_i)$$

As seen in the histogram of figure [1] there can be differences in the number of the events recorded in many orders of magnitude, meaning that some events are especially more likely than others. That is why the binned fits for the NLL are important and covered as part of the problem. The weights W_i represent the number of events observed for each bin i of the histogram.

Figure 1: CMS analysis: The dielectron (left) and dimuon (right) invariant mass spectra observed [2].

NLL for binned fits:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n -W_i * \log(P_i)$$

The floating-point error used to be small enough so that for the main realistic use cases this error is irrelevant. We are numerically estimating the gradient of the NLL using finite differences, and if the gradients are small you need good precision in the NLL to be sensitive to these differences.

3.2 IEEE-754 standard and its limitations

When working with decimal numbers in a computer the IEEE-754 standard is used for storing the information of the numbers. The IEEE-754 standard defines both single-precision (32-bit) and double-precision (64-bit) floating point formats used to represent real numbers in computers. These formats allocate a specific number of bits for the exponent and the mantissa, which determines their ability to store either very small or very large numbers.

In double precision, a limited 11 bits are reserved for the exponent. This allows the representation of both tiny values (close to zero) and large values (up to around 10^{308}) due to the wide range of exponents. As can be seen in figure [2].

Figure 2: Double Precision IEEE-754 Floating-point standard

However, the nature of floating point representation introduces challenges when performing arithmetic operations, such as addition, due to the finite precision of the mantissa. When adding two floating point numbers with different magnitudes, the result might suffer from loss of precision or even complete cancellation of smaller values. This occurs because the limited number of mantissa bits cannot fully capture the finer details of both numbers, leading to rounding errors, as can be seen in the following Python example:

```
>>> a = 1000000
>>> b = 0.000000000000001
>>> a+b
1000000.0
```

Listing 3: Example of floating point error when adding two numbers.

The addition results in the loss of information from the smaller number b , leading to a final result that does not accurately reflect the intended arithmetic. This phenomenon underscores the importance of understanding the limitations of floating point representation and its impact on numerical computations.

3.3 Kahan-Summation algorithm

The Kahan-Summation algorithm is a mathematical algorithm designed by William Kahan [3] which minimises the error made by the floating point operations. Using a compensated "curry"

which stores the lost low-order bits in each of the iterations of the algorithm. This variable is subtracted in the next iteration of the algorithm, reducing the error made. The pseudocode of this algorithm is provided here [4].

```
function KahanSum(input)
    var sum = 0.0
    var c = 0.0 // A running compensation for lost low-order bits

    for i = 1 to input.length do
        var y = input[i] - c // c is zero the first time around
        var t = sum + y
        c = (t - sum) - y // Subtracting y recovers negative (low part of y)
        sum = t // Algebraically, c should always be zero
    next i

    return sum
```

Listing 4: Kahan Summation algorithm in pseudocode.

3.4 Implementation in CUDA

To implement the Kahan Summation in the GPU, we have to take into account the needs and intricacy of the algorithm itself. First, the algorithm's iterative nature must be efficiently parallelized to leverage the GPU's computational power fully. Memory management is critical, necessitating the allocation of appropriate memory for intermediate variables such as compensated sums and carry information, due to the carry needs to be distributed through the iteration of the algorithm (and hence, through the threads). In the implementation I made, I am using shared memory of size $2 * N_{threads/block}$ to store both, the current summation and the carry, in a way that the threads of each of the blocks have access to the value of the carry and the current summation.

All the threads are launched, and they start initializing shared memory and the final resulting variable (this is done only by one of the threads). In the next iterations of the algorithm, the number of working threads is going to be reduced by half, so that the working threads are going to sum their corresponding value in the array (both sum current value and carry) plus the one corresponding to the idle threads. This behaviour can be achieved with the for loop and the if condition in [5]. With it, we are achieving this parallel reduction [3] for the threads of the block, taking advantage of the fastest memory access techniques available for this GPU architecture.

```
for (int i = blockDim.x / 2; i > 0; i >>= 1) {
    if (threadIdx.x < i && (threadIdx.x + i) < n) {
        .
        .
        .
    }
}
```

Listing 5: Header for reducing the number of working threads to half (where n is the size of the array).

Figure 3: Parallel reduction schema in NVIDIA GPU [5].

3.5 Benchmarks

It is interesting to see the benchmark that compares the execution of the GPU with the CPU (one node) to see how bad is the performance of the GPU when you are using a few data (for example in figure [4] with only 10,000 values in the array) compared to when the size of the problem starts to increase. The kernel was invoked with a block size (or number of threads per block) of 512 threads and a grid size (or number of blocks) equal to $N + (threadsPerBlock - 1)/threadsPerBlock$, being N the size of the array. Notice that the horizontal axis of the graph is in logarithmic scale and we are achieving a speedup of 8 when the size of the problem is 100 million elements.

Normal values of speedup comparing GPU with one core of CPU are normally bigger. My supervisors and I have a hypothesis of what can be affecting the unexpected performance of the algorithm. The algorithm applied for doing the reduction is putting in an idle state half of the threads in each iteration. As the number of blocks deployed for the kernel depends on the size of the array, each of the threads has a position in the array assigned, so the more time passes in the execution the fewer threads are working. So that, this is potentially decreasing the performance of the program.

It is important to remark as well that these benchmarks were done with double-precision floating-point variables in a GeForce RTX 3060 (which is a gaming NVIDIA GPU) in which the ratio between single-precision floating-point arithmetic units and double-precision floating-point arithmetic units is 32:1. Much better results are expected in an HPC centre, where the

ratio between single-precision and double-precision arithmetic units in the GPUs is 2:1. That is 16 times more double precision units than in the GeForce RTX 3060 GPU.

Figure 4: Speedup between GPU (GeForce RTX 3060) and CPU (AMD Ryzen 7 5700G) with one node.

These benchmarks for the CPU were done with only one node for the convenience of the benchmark tool we were using, given that the main objective of this part of the project was not to lower the efficiency of the Kahan-Summation algorithm when implementing it in the GPU backend, it is still worth to see the differences in this graph with only one node in the CPU. However, the best practice to see if the implementation in the GPU is outperforming the CPU is using all the nodes available in the CPU.

3.6 More

All the code is available at:

- [RooBatchCompute.cu](#)
- [RooBatchCompute.cxx](#)

4 Numeric integration in the GPU

Numeric integral approximations are necessary when dealing with complex functions because many real-world functions are not amenable to exact analytical integration. Complex functions may lack closed-form solutions or possess intricate mathematical properties that make integration by traditional methods impractical or impossible. Numeric integration provides a versatile approach to computing definite integrals by discretizing the integration domain into smaller intervals and approximating the integral using techniques such as the trapezoidal rule, Simpson’s rule, or Romberg’s method. These methods allow us to handle various complex functions

that arise in science, engineering, and other fields, providing a numerical solution that can offer valuable insights, even when analytical solutions are elusive.

Figure 5: Romberg's method illustration [6].

Romberg's method [5] is a numerical integration technique that iteratively refines approximations to definite integrals. It starts by calculating the trapezoidal rule for a given interval, then iteratively combines these results to achieve higher accuracy. By successively reducing the step size and incorporating the Richardson extrapolation, Romberg's method converges to a more precise estimation of the integral, providing a more accurate approximation than a single application of the trapezoidal rule.

This last part of the project was not possible to implement during the program, and it remains one of the future projects on which I will continue working on.

5 Conclusions and good practises

Within the context of the RooFit project, my work helped refine numerical precision in GPU-based likelihood evaluations, aligning them with the accuracy achieved by the CPU implementation. Notably, this optimization was accomplished without introducing any noteworthy new overhead.

To sum up, these are some of the lessons learned during this project and the good practices to follow when implementing algorithms for NVIDIA GPUs:

- Utilizing GPUs for datasets smaller than 10^7 entries may not yield substantial performance gains due to data transfer and parallelization overheads.
- Synchronization between threads within a block on a GPU demands meticulous attention to prevent contention and ensure efficient parallel execution.
- Ensuring that all GPU cores are optimally engaged in processing tasks can maximize computational throughput and capitalize on the hardware's potential.
- In case conditions are used, we have to be aware that they can delay other threads' executions since all the threads inside a warp are executed in an SM (Stream Multiprocessor) and they all have to be executing the same code, even if some of the threads did not go into the if condition. However, there are situations where "if" conditions are inevitable and necessary.

6 References

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